

Effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilator admitted at selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT

INTRODUCTION: This study investigates the Effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilator admitted at selected hospitals.

METHOD: Used the quantitative research approach. The Pre experimental, one-shot case design only was used. This study was developed based on Modified King's goal attainment theory. 30 samples were selected as per the inclusion criteria using the non-probability convenience sampling technique. The accessible population consisted of patients with non-invasive ventilators. The investigator explained everything about the communion board and how to use it. The communion board was kept beside the patient's bed. The investigator observed each patient for 24 hours. As the intervention it was observed that the patients in non-invasive ventilators were able to communicate their needs as per the communion board.

RESULT:

Section 1: Demographic data of sample

- ❖ 16.7% of the patients on non-invasive ventilators were aged 18-37 years, 46.7% of them were aged 37.1-56 years and 36.7% of them were aged 56.1-75 years.
- ❖ 53.3% of them were males, 43.3% of them were females and 3.3% of them were transgender.
- ❖ 3.3% of them did not have formal education, 20% of them had primary education, 46.7% of them had higher secondary education and 30% of them had graduated.
- ❖ 40% of them were employed, 33.3% of them were unemployed and 26.7% of them were self-employed.
- ❖ 46.7% of them had cardiac disorders, 30% of them had respiratory disorders, 13.3% of them had neurological disorders, 6.7% of them had nephrological disorders and 3.3% of them had other disorders.
- ❖ 6.7% of them had mild consciousness and 23.3% of them had moderate consciousness.

Section 2: To assess the effectiveness of the developed communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals.

6.7% of the patients on non-invasive ventilators had a moderate need and 93.3% of them had an extreme need for developed communication board.

Section 3: Analysis of data related to the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables.

Fisher's exact test for the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables. Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables were found to have a significant association with the need for developed communication board.

CONCLUSIONS:

The study evaluated the Effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals.

Keywords: Communion board, communication, non-invasive ventilator.

INTRODUCTION:

The transfer of ideas and information from one person to another is known as communication. It entails the sender sending thoughts, feelings, and information to the recipient. Only when both parties understand the precise details or concepts being communicated, will there be effective communication. Good plans might fail for a variety of reasons, many of which are the direct result of individuals failing to see things through to the end. [1]

Effective communication is crucial for conveying a patient's basic physiological and psychological needs, as well as their decisions, wants, and aspirations regarding their care and end of life, to a ventilator-dependent patient. Decisions can be communicated in a variety of ways, such as through gestures, head nods, mouthing words, writing, using letters, drawings, boards, and common words.

Patients in critical condition are often treated with mechanical ventilation. This kind of treatment is frequently used for respiratory issues. The purpose of mechanical ventilation is to preserve the patient's lungs by supplying oxygen and ventilation while the underlying causes of the lung disease are being addressed. While patients gain specifically from assisted ventilation, there are drawbacks as well, such as stress, insomnia, social isolation, and speech impairment.

Verbal communication is not possible in situations like a person who has a head injury, stages of coma, or respiratory distress, and patients who are on mechanical ventilator support in many critical disease conditions. In such a situation, both the messenger and receiver use a non-verbal form of communication technique. Non-verbal forms of communication can occur through gesturing, nodding the head, mouthing, signals, facial expressions, body language, writing, moving and lips movement, etc. Each individual is unique and each one will develop their expressive techniques, which is easy for them to communicate. Mechanical ventilated patients experience many barriers to communicate their needs. The lack of ability to communicate with care providers and family during periods of mechanical ventilation results in high-risk situations. Healthcare practitioners can include interpreting a patient's nonverbal forms of communication such as mouthing, gesticulating, nodding, and writing. Such non-verbal methods not only require energy but are tiring and emotionally draining for these patients. [2]

Everybody communicates in a variety of methods and circumstances, and communication plays a fundamental role in our lives. One of the hardest situations for mechanically ventilated patients is not being able to communicate verbally or with the help of assistive technology, which makes them angry and depressed. As a result, aided communication techniques ought to be widely used to enhance communication in patients on mechanical ventilation. Appel-Hardin (1984) initially introduced the communication board method as one of these ways. This board contains information about the basic needs of patients, such as names of spouses and family members, pictures of bodily parts, and information about pain and hunger. Research on communicating with aware intubated patients utilizing communication boards revealed that doing so improves patient satisfaction and lowers their feelings of hopelessness and fear. Patients on mechanical ventilation can have a more effective means of communicating with physicians and nurses by using a communication board. The primary information source for patients, families, and other multidisciplinary team members is frequently a nurse. [3]

A holistic, scientific approach to nursing care is stressed nowadays, and it is the responsibility of nurses to guarantee that patients receive this kind of care. The nurse will be able to determine the patient's wants and limitations by using one of these communication boards. Patient satisfaction and communication patterns can both be enhanced by this kind of communication board. Healthcare providers are in need to enhance effective communication of mechanically ventilated patients to promote communication. Healthcare providers can facilitate the communication of mechanically ventilated patients by offering verbal reassurance and being present and available at the bedside. Improving communication could be achieved using a communication board to standardize the approach of selecting various augmentative and alternative communication (AAC) methods. [4]

METHODS:

Study Design: Quantitative, pre-experimental, one-shot case design [5]

Research Approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach. [6]

Setting: Selected hospitals of the city [7]

Sampling Technique: Non probability, convenient sampling technique. [8]

Population: Patients on non – invasive ventilators [9]

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants.

Post-intervention the needs of the patients on non- invasive ventilators were assessed. The data was collected from 05/01/2025 to 24/01/2025

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION:

- a) Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct research.
- b) Approval from the ICU Charge.
- c) Explain the purpose of the research to the participants.
- d) Obtain informed consent (written) from the participants.

METHOD OF SELECTION OF STUDY SUBJECTS (ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA)

- a) Inclusive criteria:** Patients who are
- willing to participate in the study
 - on non-invasive ventilation
 - hemodynamically stable
 - with normal GCS (13-15)
 - above the age of 18 years
 - able to understand Marathi and English language
- b) Exclusive criteria:** Patients who are
- mechanically ventilated with a Tracheostomy tube
 - not willing to participate
 - hemodynamically unstable

c) Withdrawal criteria:

- Samples can be withdrawn from research at any point of time during the data collection

DATA ANALYSIS:SAMPLE SIZE: For the study sample size was 30, and there were only an experimental group.

The formula used for sample size was

$$n = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2,$$

Where, $Z_{\alpha/2}$ is the critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96),

MOE is the margin of error,

p is the prevalence

For our calculations,

$$Z_{\alpha/2}=1.96$$

$$P= 0.000354$$

$$MOE= 0.007$$

$$n = (1.96)^2 * 0.000354 (1 - 0.000354) / (0.007)^2$$

$$= 3.8416 * 0.000354 (0.999646) / 0.000049$$

$$= 0.00135945 / 0.000049$$

$$= 27.7438487$$

$$= 28$$

The sample size, n comes to be 28. You can select 30 samples.

RESULT:**Section I: Demographic Variables****Summary of demographic data:****Age:**

16.7% of the patients on non-invasive ventilators were aged 18-37 years, 46.7% of them had age 37.1-56 years and 36.7% of them had age 56.1-75 years.

Gender:

53.3% of them were males, 43.3% of them were females and 3.3% of them were transgender.

Education:

3.3% of them did not have formal education, 20% of them had primary education, 46.7% of them had higher secondary education and 30% of them had graduated.

Occupation:

40% of them were employed, 33.3% of them were unemployed and 26.7% of them were self-employed.

Diagnosis:

46.7% of them had a cardiac disorder, 30% of them had a respiratory disorder, 13.3% of them had a neurological disorder, 6.7% of them had a nephrological disorder and 3.3% of them had other disorders.

Glasgow coma scale:

76.7% of them had mild consciousness and 23.3% of them had moderate consciousness.

Section II**Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals**

6.7% of them disagreed, 20% of them agreed and 73.3% of them strongly agreed that the communication board is easy to understand. 6.7% of them disagreed, 13.3% of them agreed and 80% of them strongly agreed that the communication board can convey patient's needs. 6.7% of them agreed and 93.3% of them strongly agreed that the communication board helps to express difficulties. 26.7% of them agreed and 73.3% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to express patient's emotions. 23.3% of them disagreed, 16.7% of them agreed and 60% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to communicate the level of pain. 23.3% of them agreed and 76.7% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to provide comfort to patients. 3.3% of them agreed and 96.7% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to call patient's relatives. 3.3% of them disagreed, 3.3% of them agreed and 93.3% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to call healthcare workers. 10% of them agreed and 90% of them strongly agreed that a communication board is effective for communication. 60% of them strongly disagreed, 30% of them disagreed, 3.3% of them agreed and 6.7% of them strongly agreed that a communication board is time-consuming. 3.3% of them strongly disagreed, 43.3% of them disagreed, 50% of them agreed and 3.3% of them strongly agreed that the patient can respond appropriately to the Communication board. 3.3% of them disagreed, 93.3% of them agreed and 3.3% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to understand patient problems. 30% of them strongly disagreed, 66.7% of them disagreed and 3.3% of them strongly agreed that they recommend the use of a communion board to all patients having communication difficulties. 90% of them agreed and 10% of them strongly agreed that a communication board helps to maintain adequate interaction with staff nurse/health care team members. 66.7% of them agreed and 33.3% of them strongly agreed that a communication board gives satisfaction to patients and the health care team.

Section III**Analysis of data related to the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables**

Fisher's exact test was used for the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables. Since all the p-values were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables were found to have significant association with the need of developed communication board.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations.

- A similar study may be replicated on large samples, thereby findings can be generalized.
- The study can be replicated in different settings.
- The study can be replicated by changing the samples for the study.
- A similar study can be conducted with different research designs and large samples.
- The communion board used in this study can be modified further with voice modulations or any with permissions.
- Integrate the alarming communion board into daily nursing assessments as a routine part of care for NIV patients.

- To ensure that nurses feel confident using the alarming communion board, nursing schools and hospitals can develop simulation scenarios where nurses practice using the board in a safe, controlled environment. This will build competence and confidence.
- Investigate the impact of involving family members in using the board to communicate with NIV patients.
- This study can be carried out as long-term research for better findings.
- Routine audits and patient and staff satisfaction surveys can be done to monitor the effectiveness of tool.

ABBREVIATIONS:

1. AAC: Augmentative and alternative communication
2. NIV: non-invasive ventilator
3. LTOT: Long-term oxygen therapy
4. BPAP: Bilevel Positive Airway Pressure
5. COPD: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disorder
6. ICU: Intensive care unit
7. HIMV: Home invasive ventilator
8. WHO: World Health Organization

SECTION I

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

Table no.1: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their age in terms of frequency and percentage:

n =30

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage
18 - 37 years	5	16.7%
37.1 – 56 years	14	46.7%
56.1 - 75 years	11	36.7%

Table no. 2: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their gender in terms of frequency and percentage:

n =30

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	16	53.3%
Female	13	43.3%

Transgender	1	3.3%
Not to be specified	0	0%

Table no.3: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their education in terms of frequency and percentage:

n=30

Education	Frequency	Percentage
No Formal Education	1	3.3%
Primary	6	20.0%
Higher Secondary	14	46.7%
Graduate	9	30.0%
Post Graduate/ Doctorate	0	0%

Table no. 4: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their occupation in terms of frequency and percentage:

n= 30

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Employed	12	40.0%
Unemployed	10	33.3%
Self-employed	8	26.7%

Table no.5: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their diagnosis in terms of frequency and percentage:

n= 30

Diagnosis	Frequency	Percentage
Cardiac disorder	14	46.7%
Respiratory disorder	9	30.0%

Neurological disorder	4	13.3%
Nephrological disorder	2	6.7%
Others	1	3.3%

Table no.6: Description of samples (patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals) based on their Glasgow coma scale in terms of frequency and percentage:

n = 30

Glasgow coma scale	Frequency	Percentage
Mild (13-15)	23	76.7%
Moderate (9-12)	7	23.3%
Severe (3-8)	0	0.0%

SECTION II

Analysis of data related to the effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals

Table no. 7: To assess the effectiveness of the developed communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals.

n =30

Need	Frequency	Percentage
Less	0	0.0%
Moderate	2	6.7%
Extreme	28	93.3%

Section III

Analysis of data related to the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables

Table 8 : Fisher's exact test for the association of the need for a developed communication board with demographical variables.

Demographic variable		Need		p-value
		Extreme	Moderate	
Age	18 - 37 years	5	0	0.276
	37.1 – 56 years	14	0	
	56.1 - 75 years	9	2	
Gender	Male	15	1	1.000
	Female	12	1	
	Transgender	1	0	
Education	No formal education	1	0	0.710
	Primary	6	0	
	Higher Secondary	12	2	
	Graduate	9	0	
Occupation	Employed	12	0	0.168
	Unemployed	8	2	
	Self-employed	8	0	
Diagnosis	Cardiac disorder	12	2	0.710
	Respiratory disorder	9	0	
	Neurological disorder	4	0	
	Nephrological disorder	2	0	
	Other	1	0	
Glasgow coma scale	Mild (13-15)	21	2	1.000
	Moderate (9-12)	7	0	
	Severe (3-8)	0	0	

n =30

FIG NO.1 (Pie chart diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to age.)

n =30

FIG NO .2 (Pie chart diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to gender)

FIG NO.3 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to the education.)

n=30

FIG NO 4 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to the occupation)

n=30

FIG NO.5 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to the diagnosis.)

n=30

FIG NO.6 (Pie chart diagram showing the percentage-wise distribution according to the Glasgow Coma Scale.)

n=30

FIG NO.7 (Pie Chart showing percentage-wise distribution according to the alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilator admitted at selected hospitals.

FIG NO.8 (Bar diagram showing percentage-wise distribution according to the item analysis)

I AM/ मला

I WANT/ मला पाहिजे

0 NO HURT

2 HURTS
LITTLE BIT

4 HURTS
LITTLE MORE

6 HURTS
EVEN MORE

8 HURTS
WHOLE LOT

10 HURTS
WORST

PAIN SCALE/वेदना स्केल

FIG NO .9. BLUEPRINT OF COMMUNION BOARD

CONCLUSION

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of developing an alarming communion board as a need assessment tool for patients on non-invasive ventilators admitted at selected hospitals. The study made use of Pre experimental, one-shot case design only. The study population consisted of patients who were on non-invasive ventilators and admitted to selected hospitals in the city. Data was collected from 30 samples from selected hospitals in the city. Findings were recorded according to the tool. The data was gathered using descriptive and inferential statistics. Fisher's exact test was used to find an association between selected demographic variables. The study findings suggested that the developed communion board was more effective for communication as 93.3% of the needs were assessed by the investigator.

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